

WorldCereal

Validation Report

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Version 1.0 to 1.1

RID	Section	Problem	Change
	All document	Minor editing in sentences	Accepted
	3.2	Question on laco-wiki campaign	Sentence updated on the use of laco wiki to check suitability of copernicus4geoglam in situ data for validation.
	3.4	Question on AEZ product missing	For two neighboring AEZ in Nigeria one has a second maize season product and the other doesn't have a second maize season. As such the abrupt change in products is explainable

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Acronyms and abbreviations

AEZ	Agro-Ecological Zones
AMIS	Agricultural Market Information System
ASIS	Agricultural Stress Index System
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
CM4AMIS	Crop Monitor for AMIS
CM4EW	Crop Monitor for Early Warning
DDF	Design Definition File
DJF	Design Justification File
ESA	European Space Agency
EWoC	ESA WorldCereal
EOS	End of season
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agricultural Organisation
G20	Group of Twenty
GEO	Group on Earth Observation
GEOGLAM	Group on Earth Observations Global Agricultural Monitoring Initiative
GIEWS	Global Information and Early Warning System on Food and Agriculture
IGC	the International Grain Council
JECAM	Joint Experiment for Crop Assessment and Monitoring
LC	Land Cover
LPIS	Land Parcel Information System
LU	Land Use
MoA	Ministry of Agriculture
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
RDM	Reference data module
SOS	Start of season
TS	Technical Specifications document
URD	User Requirements document
USAID	United States Agency for International Development

1 Introduction

1.1 WorldCereal

WorldCereal is a project funded by the European Space Agency (ESA) and aims to develop an efficient, agile and robust EO based system allowing global and detailed agricultural monitoring. More specifically, the open-source WorldCereal system allows any user to create detailed (10 m resolution), seasonally updated maps on cropland extent, crop type (specifically for maize and wheat) and irrigation practices, the latter differentiating between actively irrigated and rainfed fields. To this end, the system builds on (1) open-and free satellite data, such as Sentinel-1, -2, and Landsat 8 and relevant in situ data, (2) newly developed and tested state-of-the-art classification algorithms, (3) the necessary cloud infrastructure to perform the work and (4) a visualization tool to view and derive useful information from the produced maps.

1.2 Purpose and scope of this document

This document is the validation report of the WorldCereal products for 2021.

The list of validated products includes:

- Temporary cropland extent, a binary map for crops with a less-than-one-year growing cycle. Sugar cane, asparagus and cassava are also considered as annual crops, even though they remain in the field for more than one year.
- Seasonal crop type products as binary maps for the maize and wheat growing seasons as defined by the global crop calendars [1], showing where maize and cereals are grown. Cereals include wheat, barley and rye.
- Seasonally irrigated cropland, defined by the WorldCereal system as a piece of land that is extensively irrigated during a specific growing season where without irrigation applied at regular intervals, the yield of this cropland would be significantly reduced or non-existent.
- Active cropland maps by seasons.

The validation report includes the description of validation approach for each product, description of the data sets used for validation, and the validation results at different levels, and conclusions.

2 Validation Approach

Validation approach differs from product to product, depending on quality and availability of reference data sets that were not used to train the models.

2.1 Temporary Cropland

We followed the guidelines for rigorous accuracy assessment provided by Stehman and Foody [2] and Szantoi et al [3]. The key validation principles we followed include: (1) quality reference data, sampling, and error matrix remain core elements of validation; (2) map relevant analyses must reflect reality of study area mapped; (3) probability sampling and design-based inference are critical to statistical rigor; (3) reproducibility of analysis; (4) detailed documentation.

2.1.1 Sample design

To validate the temporary cropland products, the IIASA team has created a new validation data set, which is completely independent from all other existing maps or reference data sets, and which is in line with the cropland definitions and mapping period of the WorldCereal products. The sampling design of the validation data set is probabilistic with random distribution of sample sites [4]. The validation sample sites were generated before the WorldCereal products were produced. Therefore, to avoid issues with inclusion probabilities, we selected a random sample design in equal area projection (Goode Homolosine). Considering that the arable land covers approximately up to 10% of all land, the sample size was 50 000 unique sample sites, with possibly up to 5 000 sample sites labelled as cropland. Figure 1 shows the spatial distribution of the validation data set.

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of the validation data set

2.1.2 Response design

Response design has been implemented in Geo-Wiki application [[5] where each validation sample site has been visually interpreted by a few IIASA experts. To decide if this is an active cropland in each period, the experts looked at very high-resolution Google historical imagery [[6] and Google Street level images, Microsoft Bing images, ESRI imagery, Planet historical data, Sentinel-2 time series, and Modis NDVI time series. Figure 2 demonstrates the Geo-Wiki interface for validation data collection with the tools to access the sources of information mentioned above. The experts were asked to label windows of 5 by 5 Sentinel pixels (each pixel 10m by 10m) either as “winter crops”, as “summer crops”,

as “maize” (if this was possible), as “active crops” (where it was not possible to confirm a growing season, e.g. overlap between seasons was too big or crop fields were too small in size), as “no crops”, or as “not sure” (where was too little information available for 2021). There was an additional question on the irrigation system (either “circle”, “other irrigation”, “rainfed”, or “not sure”).

Figure 2: The Geo-Wiki interface for the validation data collection

As already mentioned, a few IIASA experts were involved in labelling the validation data set. As seen on Figure 1, some areas are obviously noncropland. Therefore, to make the validation more efficient, those samples were checked only once, and in other cases the validation samples were classified by two different experts. To decide which validation sample sites should be classified only once or two times, we used global agro-ecological zones (<https://gaez.fao.org/>), that included land suitability for agriculture as one of the indicators for stratification. The validation sample sites where the experts disagreed on cropland presence were revisited and revised. Figure 3 shows the distribution of validation samples, with information on which sample sites were classified once, which twice, and which were revised. The highest number of sample sites that were revised was observed in Africa, in the sub-Saharan region.

Figure 3: Number of classifications per validation sample site, including the sample sites that were revised

The spatial extent of the WorldCereal products is smaller than the spatial extent of the validation data set. Therefore, we filtered out those sample sites that fall outside of the WorldCereal products, and got 35 760 valid validation sample sites in total. Figure 4 shows the distribution of the validation data set further used in the validation. It is important to note that the number of observations of active irrigation was too small to be used for the validation of irrigation products, and was therefore discarded. Also, in many cases, the experts agreed on cropland presence but had difficulties to define a growing season (e.g., two maize seasons with considerable overlap or too very small cropland fields). This information was discarded from the validation analysis.

Figure 4: The final validation data set used to validate the WorldCereal temporary cropland in 2021

2.1.3 Accuracy metrics

By using the new validation data set, we calculated confusion matrices with accuracy metrics such as overall accuracy and user's and producer's accuracies [3]. To calculate 95% confidence intervals for each metric, we applied bootstrapping with replacement [3]. All the calculations were done at global level and by continents.

2.2 Crop type

2.2.1 A new validation data set on crop type

The coverage and availability of crop type information for the year 2021 is limited. Therefore, to get a global overview of the quality of the crop type products, we decided to invest into a new crop type validation data set. This data set was created by using a new IIASA tool, called "Street Imagery validation", where users could check street level images (e.g., Google Street Level images, Mapillary etc.) and identify the crop type where it is possible. The main advantage of this tool is that there are plenty of georeferenced images with dates, going back in time. The main disadvantage is that users need to check plenty of images, and there will be only a few images where they can clearly see cropland fields that are mature enough to be identified. To make the data collection more efficient, we provided our experts with a preliminary map of points in agricultural areas where street level images are available for the year 2021. Then the experts, in an opportunistic way, checked those locations. Figure 5 shows the screenshot of the street imagery validation tool with 3 main windows: bottom - points where street level imagery is available (selected for a certain task), top right – window with street level image, top left – window to delineate a certain cropland field with identified location of street level image and direction. The dates of the viewed image are read and saved automatically

with submitted polygons and crop type information. The bottom window also indicates the overall progress on data collection for the year 2021. Points in turquoise were not yet checked by the experts, points in red were visited and crop type was detected, and points in orange were visited but not crop type observed.

Figure 5: Screenshot of the street imagery validation tool, showing a polygon where wheat parcel was identified on the Google Street View photograph. The dates for the street photograph shown on the left and the sentinel imagery on the right are matched. The world map below shows in turquoise locations with crop-potential available in Google Street View. Visited locations are shown in orange whereas locations where crop type and/or irrigation systems have been identified are shown in red.

In total, we collected around 4 745 unique crop type observations for the year 2021, from which only 3394 matched the growing seasons of the WorldCereal products. This data set is completely independent from all the existing maps and the reference data sets. Since it is not a subset from the training data set, there are no potential issues related to spatial autocorrelation between training and validation data sets. However, it has a limitation – the sample design is not probabilistic. Figure 6 shows the distribution of crop type validation data set. There are large gaps in Africa, because there were too few street-level images available for the year 2021.

Figure 6: The crop type validation data set 2021

By using the new validation data set on crop type, we calculated a confusion matrix with metrics, which we called overall agreement and agreement by classes. We did not use term “accuracy” since the sample design is not probabilistic.

2.2.2 Comparison with country-specific in-situ data sets

We have checked the reference in-situ data sets with crop type information available in the WorldCereal Reference Module (<https://worldcereal-rdm.geo-wiki.org/map/>). We selected only those data sets that are for the year 2021 and cross-checked which records were not used in training the models.

Here is the list of datasets used for comparison:

- Annual Crop Inventory Ground Truth Data, Canada, 2021 (AAFC);
- FAO WAPOR, Sri Lanka, 2021;
- Copernicus4GEOGLAM, Kenya, 2021;
- Copernicus4GEOGLAM, Tanzania, 2021;
- Copernicus4GEOGLAM, Uganda, 2021;
- FAO WAPOR, Mozambique, 2021;
- LPIS LATVIA, 2021;
- LPIS Belgium (Flanders), 2021;
- LPIS Austria, 2021;
- ESYCRE, Spain, 2021.

If in-situ records were points, we directly used the coordinates and extracted crop type values from the WorldCereal products to those points. If in-situ records were polygons, we used the centroids and extracted crop type values from the WorldCereal products to those centroids. Then we calculated agreement for each crop type following the same approach as for calculating user's and producer's accuracies.

2.2.3 Comparison with country specific crop type maps

Additionally, we have compared the WorldCereal crop type products with the USDA National Agricultural Statistics Service Cropland Data Layer 2021 (<https://croplandcros.scinet.usda.gov/>). For

comparison, we randomly generated points over the extent of each map and then extracted values from the WorldCereal maize and wheat products and the USDA map.

2.3 Active Cropland

Initially, while collecting data for validating temporary cropland products, the experts also answered the question about active croplands in each season. However, since the definition of cropland active in a season since then changed (from including either planting or harvesting, or both events, to including both events), we cannot use the collected data anymore.

2.4 Active Irrigation

The amount of total land that is being irrigated differs from year to year, depending a lot on climate. As it has been mentioned in the description of training data, there is very limited information available about actual irrigation of cropland fields, giving us little means to run validation of irrigation products as such and by seasons. Here, to carry on a qualitative assessment, we have spatially compared the WorldCereal products with two data sets that are of open access:

- Global map of areas equipped for irrigation expressed as percentages, produced by FAO[7];
- Landsat-Derived Global Rainfed and Irrigated-Cropland Product at 30 meters [8].

For comparison, the WorldCereal seasonal irrigation products were combined and aggregated to the FAO map., expressing percentages of irrigated land in 2021. The LGRIP30 map has been also aggregated to the FAO map. We have also compared the WorldCereal irrigation products with data on irrigated land from The World Factbook from the CIA (<https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/field/irrigated-land/>). The results of the comparison are shown as figures.

2.5 Qualitative assessment

In addition to the quantitative assessment, we have visually checked all the layers for artefacts. Such a visual check was done in the Geo-Wiki application.

3 Validation Results

3.1 Temporary Cropland

Tables 1 to 7 show confusion matrices for temporary cropland assessment at global level and by continents. In each table, the rows correspond to the WorldCereal products, while the columns to the validation data set.

Table 1: Confusion matrix for temporary cropland assessment at global level

WorldCereal cropland/ Geo-Wiki validation data set	No cropland	Cropland	User's accuracy
No cropland	30601	299	99,0%
Cropland	452	3488	88,5%
Producer's accuracy	98,5%	92,1%	
Overall accuracy			97,8%

Table 2: Confusion matrix for temporary cropland assessment in Africa

WorldCereal cropland/ Geo-Wiki validation data set	No cropland	Cropland	User's accuracy
No cropland	7405	80	98,9%
Cropland	148	487	76,7%
Producer's accuracy	98,0%	85,9%	
Overall accuracy			97,2%

Table 3: Confusion matrix for temporary cropland assessment in Asia

WorldCereal cropland/ Geo-Wiki validation data set	No cropland	Cropland	User's accuracy
No cropland	10012	86	99,1%
Cropland	227	1318	85,3%
Producer's accuracy	97,8%	93,9%	
Overall accuracy			97,3%

Table 4: Confusion matrix for temporary cropland assessment in Australia and Oceania

WorldCereal cropland/ Geo-Wiki validation data set	No cropland	Cropland	User's accuracy
No cropland	1514	5	99,7%
Cropland	12	123	91,1%
Producer's accuracy	99,2%	96,1%	

Overall accuracy	99,0%
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Table 5: Confusion matrix for temporary cropland assessment in Europe

WorldCereal cropland/ Geo-Wiki validation data set	No cropland	Cropland	User's accuracy
No cropland	2552	49	98,1%
Cropland	23	644	96,6%
Producer's accuracy	99,1%	92,9%	
Overall accuracy			97,8%

Table 6: Confusion matrix for temporary cropland assessment in North America

WorldCereal cropland/ Geo-Wiki validation data set	No cropland	Cropland	User's accuracy
No cropland	4207	39	99,1%
Cropland	25	539	95,6%
Producer's accuracy	99,4%	93,3%	
Overall accuracy			98,7%

Table 7: Confusion matrix for temporary cropland assessment in South America

WorldCereal cropland/ Geo-Wiki validation data set	No cropland	Cropland	User's accuracy
No cropland	4911	40	99,2%
Cropland	17	377	95,7%
Producer's accuracy	99,7%	90,4%	
Overall accuracy			98,9%

Table 8 summarizes the results of the validation of temporary cropland extent at global level and by continents. It includes overall accuracy, user's and producer's accuracies for cropland, as well as 95% confidence intervals calculated by applying bootstrapping with replacement. The most informative are user's and producer's accuracies, which are 88.5% and 92.1%, respectively for the globe. Overall, the accuracy numbers are very high for all the continents, while being a bit lower in Asia and Africa. Those two continents are characterised by significant coverage with very small fields and by very fragmented landscapes, and there was limited in-situ data available for training the models. The largest commission errors as well as omission errors are detected in Africa.

Table 8: Summary accuracy metrics with confidence intervals calculated using bootstrapping with replacement

Continents	Overall accuracy	95% confidence intervals for overall accuracy		User's accuracy for cropland	95% confidence intervals for user's accuracy		Producer's accuracy for cropland	95% confidence intervals for producer's accuracy	
		lower bound	higher bound		lower bound	higher bound		lower bound	higher bound
Global	97,8%	97,8%	97,9%	88,5%	88,0%	89,0%	92,1%	91,7%	92,5%
Africa	97,2%	97,0%	97,4%	76,7%	75,0%	78,3%	85,9%	84,5%	87,5%
Asia	97,3%	97,2%	97,5%	85,3%	84,4%	86,1%	93,9%	93,3%	94,5%
Australia and Oceania	99,0%	98,8%	99,2%	91,1%	89,0%	93,6%	96,1%	94,8%	98,0%
Europe	97,8%	97,6%	98,1%	96,6%	96,0%	97,2%	92,9%	92,0%	93,9%
North America	98,7%	98,5%	98,8%	95,6%	94,7%	96,5%	93,3%	92,3%	94,3%
South America	98,9%	98,8%	99,1%	95,7%	94,8%	96,8%	90,4%	89,1%	91,8%

3.2 Crop type

Table 9 shows the results of crop type validation at global level by using the new crop type validation data set collected in the Street Imagery Validation Tool (see Figure 6). For calculating the confusion matrix, maize in season 1 and season 2 was combined into the single class “maize”, spring cereals and winter cereals were also combined into the single class “cereals”. Overall, omission errors are larger than commission errors for both crop types, maize and cereals. This could be explained by the lack of training data. It is important to note that the presented results are biased towards the areas covered by the validation data set, e.g., large gaps in Africa (see Figure 6).

Table 9: Confusion matrix for crop types at global level

WorldCereal products/ Validation data set	Other crops	Maize	Cereals	Agreement by classes (User's accuracy)
Other crops	1010	167	161	75,5%
Maize	90	544	12	84,2%
Cereals	31	10	604	93,6%
Agreement by classes (Producer's accuracy)	89,3%	75,5%	77,7%	
Overall agreement				82,1%

Table 10 below summarizes the results of the comparison between the WorldCereal crop type products and the exiting country-specific in-situ data sets for 2021. We observe a very high agreement for maize and cereals in Canada and European countries. We have concerns about the quality of the in-situ data sets in Africa.

Table 10: Summary comparison with country-specific crop type data sets

In-situ data set	Maize	Cereals
Annual Crop Inventory Ground Truth Data, Canada, 2021 (AAFC)	Agreement ~ 96%	Agreement - 80% for winter and spring, main confusion is between winter and spring cereals
FAO WAPOR, Sri Lanka, 2021	Too little records (less than 30)	No records
Copernicus4GEOGLAM, Kenya, 2021	There are many records but due to quality issues we cannot use it for validation	No records, only a few in Kenya
Copernicus4GEOGLAM, Tanzania, 2021		
Copernicus4GEOGLAM, Uganda, 2021		
FAO WAPOR, Mozambique, 2021	Agreement ~70%	No records
LPIS LATVIA, 2021	Too little records	Agreement ~ 90%
LPIS Austria, 2021	Agreement - 88%	Agreement ~95%
ESYCRE, Spain, 2021	Agreement ~90%	Agreement ~85%, confusion with oats and other cereals
LPIS Belgium (Flanders), 2021	Agreement ~88%	Agreement ~ 97%

We have detected quality issues of the Copernicus4GEOGLAM data sets. The WUR team has checked all Copernicus GEOGLAM data sets (polygons) by taking a 1% sample. The percentage of suspicious cases are:

- Kenya long rains: 41%;
- Kenya short rains: 44%;
- Tanzania: 21%;
- Uganda long rains: 38%;
- Uganda short rains: 30%.

In addition, the IIASA team has taken a subset containing only maize records from the Copernicus4GEOGLAM project, looking at Kenya (long rains) and launched the Laco-Wiki campaign (<https://laco-wiki.net/c/ken2021>). We checked 100 random maize fields. Taking from the perspective of a very conservative approach (e.g., excluding potential fallow land), we found that only 32 fields out of 100 were suitable for remote sensing applications at 10m resolution. Figure 7 illustrates examples of maize polygons that we considered as not suitable for remote sensing applications at 10m resolution, especially for validation purposes.

Figure 7: Copernicus4GEOGLAM. Examples of maize polygons in Kenya that are not suitable for remote sensing applications at 10m resolution

Figure 8 illustrates an example of distribution of Copernicus4GEOGLAM original crop type point data. We have highlighted in yellow those points that are not suitable for remote sensing applications at a 10m resolution. Those are points that fall on trees, roads, between two fields, on shrubs, on fields edge, etc.

Figure 8: Copernicus4GEOGLAM. Examples of point records (in red) in Kenya that are not suitable for remote sensing applications at 10m resolution (highlighted in yellow)

The Copernicus4GEOGLAM data sets should be fully checked, and those records that do not meet requirements for remote sensing applications should be removed. In the current format, we cannot use the data sets for validation of crop type maps.

3.2.1 Comparison with country specific crop type maps

This section contains several tables to show the results of the comparison between two maps of USDA and the WC. Overall, we observe a good agreement between the two maps. We do not have any

ground truth data to determine which map is better, and both contain some errors. We see that the USDA map shows more cereals (winter and spring wheat) and there is a high confusion between soyabean and maize. Therefore, we calculated one more table where we assumed that those confusion areas could be double cropping (soybean and maize).

Table 11: Comparison with USDA crop type map 2021

WorldCereal products/USDA crop type 2021	Other crop	Maize	Cereals	Agreement by classes
Other crop	40,5%	1,9%	5,4%	84,7%
Maize	7,8%	31,8%	0,0%	80,2%
Cereals	1,7%	0,2%	10,7%	84,9%
Agreement by classes	80,9%	93,8%	66,5%	
Overall agreement				82,9%

Table 12: Comparison with USDA crop type map 2021, combining maize and soyabean

WorldCereal products/USDA crop type 2021	Other crop	Maize and Soyabean	Cereals	Agreement by classes
Other crop	40,5%	1,9%	5,4%	84,7%
Maize	1,9%	37,7%	0,0%	95,1%
Cereals	1,7%	0,2%	10,7%	84,9%
Agreement by classes	91,7%	94,7%	66,5%	
Overall agreement				88,8%

3.3 Active Irrigation

Figure 9 shows the results of the comparison of the WorldCereal irrigation products with FAO global irrigation area equipped for irrigation in 2005 map [7] (Figure 9a), the Landsat-Derived Global Rainfed and Irrigated-Cropland Product at 30 meters (LGRIP30) [8] (Figure 9b), and country statistics on irrigated land from the International Commission on Irrigation & Drainage (ICID, 2021) (Figure 9c). For this analysis, the irrigation maps from the three WorldCereal seasons are combined into a single map. This combined irrigated area map describes if in any of the three seasons within the same year a pixel is being classified as irrigated. The figures must be interpreted with caution since we do not know what the ground truth is. It is important to consider the following aspects:

- Wherever the WorldCereal irrigation products show less irrigation (areas highlighted in red), it could be that not all the areas equipped for irrigation were irrigated in 2021. This is a common practice in many countries. Also, both the FAO and LGRIP30 maps include perennial croplands in their definitions, while the WorldCereal products does not. Therefore, it is logical that those two maps show more irrigation areas in some places.
- Wherever the WorldCereal irrigation products show more irrigation (areas highlighted in blue), those pixels could be either areas recently equipped for irrigation, or WorldCereal

commission errors, or FAO's and LGRIP30 omission errors. However, we think that the hotspots in the south of the Sahel, the USA, Russia and Brazil are most likely WorldCereal commission errors.

Figure 9: Differences in percentages whilst comparing the WorldCereal combined irrigation product and: (a) the FAO global area equipped for irrigation in 2005 map, (b) the LGRIP30 irrigated area map for 2015, (c) and the ICID world irrigated area dataset. The WorldCereal products show more irrigation in blue areas and less in red areas, compared to the other datasets.

Figure 9 shows that there is a large difference between the WorldCereal irrigated area product and the LGRIP30 map. Mainly in Europe and Asia, the LGRIP30 classifies significantly more land as being irrigated. To understand how these maps relate to global statistics, Figure 10 shows a comparison between multiple global irrigation

maps from literature and statistical datasets from the Central Intelligence Agency [9] and the International Committee on Irrigation and Drainage [10].

Figure 10: Comparison between global statistical datasets from the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) and International Committee on Irrigation and Drainage (ICID) on irrigated area compared to five global irrigated area maps that are based on remote sensing data.

The two statistical datasets used for this analysis show relatively similar global irrigated area values of roughly 3 million km². The map from [7] is used to produce the area equipped for irrigation map of the FAO and describes the irrigated land around the year 2005. The studies from [11] and [12] mainly focus on long timeseries of NDVI data to determine irrigated areas. The LGRIP30 map is based on the Global Cropland-Extent Product at 30-m Resolution (GCEP30) [13] to mask agricultural areas and it combines multiple spectral bands and indices of Landsat-8 from 2014-2017 to train multiple machine learning models [8]. From the different irrigation maps, the map from [7] agrees best with the statistical datasets. Both the maps from [11] and [12] show an overestimation of irrigated areas compared to the statistical datasets. The LGRIP30 map shows a drastic overestimation of the irrigated area, which is almost double compared to the findings from the CIA and ICID. Finally, the WorldCereal irrigation product underestimates the global irrigated area by roughly 35%, which is partly due to omission errors, but also caused by the fact that the WorldCereal product only focuses on annual cropland. The year 2021 is deemed to have been a relatively wet year for Europe, South America, Australia, and parts of Southern Asia [14], so potentially many farms that are equipped for irrigation did not need to irrigate their crops. Producing more irrigated area maps for different years with the WorldCereal system should give more insight into this hypothesis. Combining irrigated area maps from different years could also add information on the irrigation frequency of each pixel.

3.4 Qualitative assessment

The results of visual inspection are summarized below for each product. It should be noted that the global 2021 WorldCereal product views are, in fact, consisting of individually processed WorldCereal products for each agro-ecological zone (AEZ) as defined in the WorldCereal system (Figure 11). Neighbouring AEZ were seamlessly aligned in the global overview but could in fact be covering significantly different crop calendars. As such, wherever neighbouring AEZ have such significant differences in their respective crop calendars, visual artefacts may be apparent on the border between such AEZ. Visual artefacts that result from this can be related to a significant extent by crop calendar inconsistencies – where for example an inaccurate part of the year could be targeted for a specific crop type - and not only by inaccurate model predictions.

Figure 11: Agro-ecological zones as defined by the WorldCereal system. Each zone has its own crop calendars and related WorldCereal products.

Temporary cropland extent

No artifacts or large-scale commission errors were detected.

Winter cereals in a tc-wintercereals season

There were no artefacts detected. We observe noisy fields or not complete fields in some places, e.g., in North America. Figure 12 shows an example of such noisy fields in Canada. The reason why some fields are not complete is that the year 2021 was not favourable for agriculture (<https://www.air-worldwide.com/blog/posts/2021/9/drought-canada-farmers-crop-insurers/>).

Figure 12: Noisy fields of winter cereals (in a tc-wintercereals season) in North America, Canada. Coordinates in lat/lon: 39.3720, -101.298

Spring cereals in a tc-springcereals season

There were no artefacts detected, only noisy fields in some places, e.g., in Eastern Europe (see Figure 12). We lack training data on spring cereals. Therefore, sometimes the predictions are uncertain. This can be checked in the confidence layers. Fields are detected as temporary cropland, but in the crop type classification, the algorithm is not confident for spring cereals and there is confusion within fields between spring and winter cereals.

Figure 12: Example of noisy fields of spring cereals (in a tc-springcereals season) in Eastern Europe. Coordinates in lat,lon: 52.3513, 38.5142

Maize in a tc-maize-main season

We detected only one artefact in Africa, which is shown on Figure 13, with the AEZ boundaries overlaid. The artefact is aligned with the boundary between AEZ 36124 and AEZ 12048. Upon closer investigation, the crop calendars for tc-maize-main are substantially different between these two AEZ. According to the International Production Assessment Division (IPAD) of the USDA (4), the country has one main maize growing season that starts between February (South) and May (North) and ends between June (South) and September (North). Only the Southern part is reported to have a second maize season from September till January. The main maize season mapped in AEZ 36124 ranges from April till December, containing the USDA reported season for the North. AEZ 12048 however covers the period from September to June, containing a potential second maize season and also the main maize season from the South. We can therefore assume that the much higher detection rate within AEZ 12048 is caused by the much broader maize season definition compared to AEZ 36124 which is more restricted in time, explaining the visual artefact on the border of the two AEZ.

Figure 13: The example of visual artefact (in Africa), related to an AEZ border, where neighbouring AEZ have substantially different crop calendars defined for tc-maize-main season. Coordinates in lat, lon: 1.8644, 31.4341

Figure 14: Uganda crop calendars according to USDA IPAD indicate one main maize (corn) season in the North and up to two maize seasons in the South.

Tc-maize-second

We observed some noisy maize fields, e.g., in Brazil (Figure 15). Our tc-maize-second crop calendar in corresponding AEZ 20087 runs from mid-October till mid-April. According to USDA IPAD crop calendars for Brazil Center-South, this is mostly aligned with the “first” corn season, though this season runs up till June. It is therefore likely that the season considered by the WorldCereal system does not

extend sufficiently in time to capture full maturity and harvest of the maize fields, therefore causing confusion.

Figure 15: The example of noisy maize fields in a tc-maize-second season, in Brazil. Coordinates in lat, lon: -13.4756, -55.2027

Figure 166 explains that the artefact in Mozambique and Malawi can be traced back to the fact that AEZ 9030 has no tc-maize-second season defined. The potential second (shorter) maize season is entirely confined within the (longer) tc-main-maize season and was therefore not processed separately. Visualizing the area for the tc-maize-main product confirms that the artefact disappears and that the product is continuous over the border between the neighbouring AEZ. Figure 17 shows another example of artefact, which would have the same explanation.

Figure 16: The artefact in Mozambique and Malawi is traced back to the fact that AEZ 9030 has no tc-maize-second season defined. The potential second (shorter) maize season is entirely confined within the (longer) tc-main-maize season.

Figure 17: The artefact in Ethiopia and Sudan (Africa) for maize in a tc-maize-second season. Coordinates in lat,lon: 9.4759, 39.5687.

Figure 18 goes into more detail about the observed artefacts in the large-scale overview of the tc-maize-second season. Three reasons were found: AEZ 38127 does not consider a tc-maize-second season and therefore has no maize product for this season. Secondly, a real artefact is observed in a region where Sentinel-1 observations were completely lacking. In this case, the system was required to run an optical-only model which in this case is less accurate and has maize commission causing the visual artefact. Finally, the abrupt maize detection change seen on the border between AEZ 32114 and

AEZ 31113 is caused by significantly different tc-maize-second calendars between both. AEZ 31113 has a crop calendar which is aligned with the reported maize crop calendar for Ethiopia by USDA IPAD. However, AEZ 32114 is mostly aligned with the sorghum season reported for Sudan, where no maize season is reported. It is therefore likely – though it cannot be confirmed without proper validation data – that the detected maize in AEZ 32114 could be partially related to sorghum fields.

Figure 18: The artefacts of maize product in a tc-maize-second season have three causes in this example. AEZ 38127 does not consider this season, and AEZ 32114 and 31113 have significantly different calendars for this season, explaining the abrupt border between both. A third explanation relates to a real artefact cause be the usage of less accurate optical-only model in a region that completely lacks Sentinel-1 radar observations.

The observed discontinuity in Nigeria is caused by the fact that the upper part of Figure 19 does not consider a tc-maize-second season and was therefore the product tc-maize second is not produced for this AEZ. This is confirmed in Figure 20 for tc-maize-main where the same region does not show visual discontinuities between the two AEZ. Figure 20 shows a similar example.

Figure 19: The artefacts of maize product in a tc-maize-second season in Nigeria (Africa). Coordinates in lat,lon: 10.0907, 7.679

Figure 20: The maize product in a tc-maize-main season does not show discontinuities between neighbouring AEZ, Nigeria, Africa

Irrigation

For irrigation detection, some obvious artifacts were identified. The most pronounced artifact was located south of the Sahel region, on the borders between Sudan, South Sudan, and Ethiopia (Figure 21). Here, for all the three seasons, the edges of the local AEZ were clearly visible and the results were decent north of the border, showing the Gezira irrigation district, but large commission errors in the irrigated area were present in the south of the border. This seems to be a direct result of the definitions of the start and end of seasons for this AEZ, but it might also be caused by the unique local landscape and climate, which were not part of our training dataset.

Figure 21: Irrigation. The artefact in the Sahel region, on the borders between Sudan, South Sudan, and Ethiopia

The second set of artifacts can be related to the inputs that are used to calculate the features. Because of the low resolution of the AgERA5 meteorological inputs, flat areas near mountain ranges show clear artifacts, which are most pronounced in the Po-valley, Italy (Figure 22). Here, in the northern half of the Po-valley, much less pixels are classified as irrigated, compared to the southern half. More striking though is that when we inspect the confidence layer of the irrigation maps during the winter season, we see that the model is very confident of its results in the northern half of the Po-valley. This means that, based on the inputs that the model has received, it deemed to have done a good job in translating these inputs to irrigated area outputs. Since the precipitation deficit is one of the main drivers in the irrigation model, snow in the mountains during the winter season might influence the calculation of the precipitation deficit, and the model therefore assumes that there was no shortage of water, which resulted in an omission of irrigated cropland. Although these artifacts are less pronounced during the other two seasons, due to the large gradients in the total seasonal precipitation amounts near mountainous areas, the results are still affected negatively.

Figure 22: Irrigation. The artefacts in the Po-valley, Italy: (a) irrigated fields in blue; (b) confidence layer

The last set of artefacts are related to the overlapping orbits of the satellites at higher latitudes, see Figure 23.

Figure 23: Irrigation. The artefacts related to the overlapping orbits of the satellites at higher latitudes.

Active cropland in a tc-maize-main season

There were no artefacts detected.

Active cropland in a tc-maize-second season

We detected artefacts in the same areas as for the irrigated product in summer season 2.

Active cropland in a tc-wintercereals season

We found artefacts in South America (Figure 24), Africa (Figure 25), and India (Figure 26).

Figure 24: Active cropland in a tc-wintercereals season (in red colour). Artefacts in Brazil and Argentina

Figure 25: Active cropland in a tc-wintercereals season (in red colour). Artefacts in Sub-Saharan Africa

Figure 26: Active cropland in a tc-wintercereals season (in red colour). Artefacts in India

The discontinuity in active cropland for tc-wintercereals in central India is linked to an AEZ boundary where slight differences in crop calendars occur (Figure 27). AEZ 28122 has a slightly shorter growing season than AEZ 28107. The strict requirement that both the detected start and end of growing season need to fall within the AEZ crop calendar causes the majority of pixels in AEZ 28122 to be partially outside the season of interest, while those same detected growing seasons fall completely inside the AEZ 28107 growing season.

Figure 27: Discontinuity in active cropland for a tc-wintercereals season in central India, linked to slightly different crop calendars.

4 Conclusion

This document reports the validation results of the WorldCereal products. Overall, the results meet the initial project requirements by the funder: minimum accuracy of 80% for global temporary cropland extent, and minimum accuracy of 70% for each crop type at global level.

Our assessment shows that the temporal cropland extent has a very high user's and producer's accuracies for cropland, which are 88.5% and 92.1%, respectively for the globe. The accuracies are a bit lower for Africa and Asia, which are characterised by very fragmented landscapes and very small fields.

We achieved good accuracies for both crop types,(maize and cereals) but the results are biased towards the spatial coverage of the validation data set. The major validation data gap is in Africa.

We would like to highlight that there is very little information available on crop types that could be used for validation, and many reference data sets have low quality or are not suitable for remote sensing applications.

There is a high potential to fill the data gaps from the past by using the street level image validation tool developed by IIASA, but such data collection would require funding.

The last and most critical point: there is too little information available about actual irrigation, even for Europe where many countries have very detailed parcel annual inventory (LPIS).

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